

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

A review: Nutritional and nutraceuticals properties of betel leaves (*Piper betle* L.)

Renuka Jandu* and Lakhwinder Kaur

Department of Home Science, KVA DAV College for Women, Karnal, Haryana, India. Affiliated to Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, Haryana, India.

Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances, 2023, 15(01), 118–124

Publication history: Received on 01 January 2023; revised on 15 February 2023; accepted on 17 February 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gjeta.2023.15.1.0030>

Abstract

Piper betel (locally known as *Paan*) belongs to the Piperaceae or pepper family and many health benefits bonded with it. Betel leaves are highly nutritive and contain considerable amount of vitamins and minerals, especially calcium, iron, potassium and β -carotene. The betel leaves possess therapeutic activities such as antioxidant activity, anti-microbial, anti-ulcerogenic, anti-haemolytic activity, anti-diabetic, immune-modulatory, anti-inflammatory, gastro protective, radio protective and cytotoxicity activity. Most of the therapeutic activities of betel leaves are due to presence of antioxidants. Scientific research on the betel leaves revealed that due to its beneficial bioactivities it has a great potential to be used in developing commercial products of enhanced medicinal and nutritional value. Many products were developed by incorporation of betel leaves such as *ladoo*, cutlets, *namkeen*, *khakhra* and *papad*. Therefore, we can use betel leaves in our day to day life to reduce the risk of many diseases. It has great potential to be incorporate in development of value added products.

Keywords: Betel leaf; Phytochemical; Biological activities; Antioxidant

1. Introduction

The betel leaf commonly known as '*Paan*' or '*Nagvalli*' (family-Piperaceae) is an evergreen and perennial creeper (Varier, 1995). Significance of leaves has been explained in relationship to every sphere of human life such as social, culture, religious and is very much relevant even in modern days. Betel leaf is an important commercial crop grown in India, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka (Guha, 2006). From ancient time betel leaves are chewed along with areca nut, slaked lime, cardamom and clove in many Asian countries. (Walter and Sofia, 2007)

This plant originates from the central and eastern part of peninsular Malaysia and which is locally known as *Sirih* (Jaganath and Ng Teik, 2000). Due to the numerous benefits, betel vine is grown for its leaves. The best conditions for cultivation of betel vine are tropical rain forests, which provide cool shade, considerable humidity and an adequate supply of soil moisture like Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand, Cambodia, Vietnam and India (Balasubrahmanyam and Rawat, 1990). Betel leaf is well known for its various uses as masticatory or better known as betel quid, which consists of fresh betel leaf, betel nut, and slaked lime paste. This edible betel leaf is traditionally used for various medicinal purposes including improved appetite, tonic for brain, antiseptic for wounds, breath refresher, etc. Scientists found that this plant possesses many beneficial bioactivities including antimutagenic, anticarcinogenic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and antidiabetic properties. [Amonkar *et al.*, 1986] Betel leaf is traditionally known to be useful for the treatment of various diseases like bad breath, boils and abscesses, conjunctivitis, constipation, headache, itches, mastitis, mastoiditis, leucorrhoea, otorrhoea, swelling of gum, rheumatism, cuts and injuries (Agarwal *et al.*, 2012).

*Corresponding author: Renuka Jandu

2. Nutritive value of betel leaf

The leaves are very nutritive and also contain substantial amount of many vitamins and minerals and therefore, six leaves with a little bit of slaked lime can be compare with 300 ml of cow milk particularly for the vitamin and mineral nutrition.

Table 1 Nutritive value of Betel leaves (fresh)

Nutrient	Quantity (Per 100g)
Moisture (g)	84.93
Protein (g)	3-3.5
Fat (g)	0.75-1.0
Dietary fiber (g)	1.97-2.3
Carbohydrate (g)	6.16-7.37
Energy (Kcal)	43.73-48.27
Calcium (mg)	207
Phosphorus (mg)	51.73-55.72
Iron (mg)	5.0-7.0
Potassium (mg)	649-678
Sodium (mg)	14.04-16.80
β -carotene (μ g)	4186-4686
Vitamin C (mg)	18.40-24.51

(IFCT, 2017); (Agarwal, et al.2012); (Ghosh et al. 2014)

Table 2 Nutritive value of Betel leaves (dry)

Nutrient	Quantity (Per 100g)
Moisture (g)	12.66-13.53
Protein (g)	12.07- 13.47
Fat (g)	4.46-4.62
Crude fiber (g)	5.2-6.2
Carbohydrate (g)	48.62
Energy (Kcal)	285.14-288.54
Calcium (mg)	2018.8-2894.2
Phosphorus (mg)	213-242.3
Iron (mg)	23.15-40.98
Potassium (mg)	3822-4054
Sodium (mg)	24.3-32.83
β -carotene (μ g)	5440-6693
Vitamin C (mg)	32.86-34.73

(Verneker et al., 2018)

3. Chemical Constituents

Phytochemical investigation on leaves revealed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrate, amino acids, tannins and steroidal components (Sugumaran *et al.*, 2011). The specific strong pungent aromatic flavour in leaves is due to phenol and terpene like bodies (Bajpai *et al.*, 2010). The leaf contains water (85-90%), proteins (3-3.5%), carbohydrates (0.5-6.1%), minerals (2.3-3.3%), fat (0.4-1%), fibre (2.3%), essential oil (0.08-0.2%), tannin (0.1-1.3%) and alkaloid (arakene). It also contains different vitamins like vitamin-C (0.005-0.01%), nicotinic acid (0.63-0.89mg/100gms), vitamin-A (1.9-2.9mg/100gms), thiamine (10-70µg/100gms), riboflavin (1.9-30µg/100gms). Beside these it contains minerals such as calcium (0.2-0.5%), iron (0.005-0.007), iodine (3.4µg/100gms), phosphorus (0.05-0.6%), potassium (1.1- 4.6%) (Guha, 2006). The fresh new leaves contain much more amount of essential oil diastase enzyme and sugar as compare to old leaves. Betel leaf also contain 'Chavicol' that is four times potent as antiseptic agent as compare to carbolic acid (Kumar *et al.*, 2010). It is a colorless liquid found together with terpenes in betel oil.

3.1. Therapeutic aspects

3.1.1. Traditional Use

Betel leaf known from ancient times as an aromatic, stimulo-carminative (CSIR, 1992) (katu), astringent and aphrodisiac [Sudriket *et al.*, 2012; Chu, 2001]. According to Indian traditional system of medicine, the leaves identified with digestive and pancreatic lipase stimulant activities (Mula *et al.*, 2008; Santhanam and Nagarajan, 1990; Chatterjee and Pakrashi, 1995; Deshpande *et al.*, 1970; Rawat *et al.*, 1989). The leaves were chewed by singers to improve their voice and also efficiency and stamina (Chandra *et al.*, 1987). The fresh betel leaves possess antimicrobial, ringworm, antifungal, antiseptic and anti-helminthic effects (Vossen and Wessel, 2000). Leaves are also used in eye drops for eye injury/infection as a baby lotion for the new born, for coughs, asthma, constipation and to arrest milk secretion (Amalia *et al.*, 2008). In folk medicine the roots were used as long lasting female oral contraceptive (Evans *et al.*, 1984). Piper betel also showed many activities such as hypotensive, cardio tonic, smooth and skeletal muscles relaxant actions (Bangar *et al.*, 1966; Ali and Mehta, 1970).

3.2. Biological Activities

3.2.1. Antimicrobial activity

The leaf has a significant antimicrobial activity against various micro-organisms (Jesonbabu *et al.*, 2012). It also shows the antimicrobial activity against *Streptococcus pyrogen*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *E.coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* etc., beside this the leaf extract also poses the bactericidal activity against the urinary tract pathogenic bacteria such as *Enterococcus faecalis*, *C.koseri*, *C.fruendi*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* etc. (Agarwal and Singh, 2012; Chakraborty and Shah, 2011). The bioactive molecules present in leaves thought to be responsible for anti-bacterial activity is sterol, which has been obtained in large quantities in betel leaf extracts.

3.2.2. Gastroprotective activity

The hot water extract of betel leaves significantly increased the mucus content adhering to the wall of the mucosa. The mucus layer is considered to be important in mucosal defences against gastric acids, and also as an agent in facilitate the repair process. Many researches proved that anti-oxidants might be effective mechanism not only in protecting against gastric mucosal injury, but also inhibiting progression of gastric ulceration. Ulceration progression is caused by free radical-induced chain process. Consequently, its arrest by radical scavengers helps in the faster healing (Majumdar *et al.*, 2003; Arambewela *et al.*, 2004).

3.2.3. Antioxidant activity

Oxidative damage is an important effect of ionizing radiation on biological membranes. It is a chain reaction (Verma *et al.*, 2010). Free radicals generated from the radiolytic decomposition of water can attack fatty acid chains of membrane lipid. A free radical that has sufficient energy to abstract an allylic hydrogen from the methylene carbon of polyunsaturated fatty acids can initiate the peroxidative process. Here the presence polyphenols compounds like catechol, allylpyrocatechol etc. in betel leaf extract inhibited the radiation induced lipid peroxidation process effectively. This could be attributed to its ability to scavenge free radicals involved in initiation and propagation steps. The extracts reduced most of the Fe³⁺ ions and possess strong reductive ability (Manigauha *et al.*, 2009). The extract also showed strong hydroxyl radical and superoxide anion radical scavenging property when compared with different standards such as ascorbic acid and BHT (Dasgupta and De, 2004; Rathee *et al.*, 2006; Pin *et al.*, 2010; Arambewela *et al.*, 2006).

3.2.4. Antidiabetic activity

The aqueous extract of betel leaves possess hypoglycaemic action when tested in fasted normoglycaemic rats (Chandra *et al.*, 2011). The betel leaf suspension, significantly reduces the blood glucose level, glycosylated haemoglobin and decreased activities of liver glucose-6-phosphatase and fructose-1, 6- bisphosphatase, whereas liver hexokinase increased in Streptozocin (STZ) diabetic rats compared with untreated diabetic rats. The ability of lowering blood glucose level of Streptozocin (STZ) induced diabetic rat gives a suggestion that the betel leaf extract have the insulin-omimetic activity (Arambewela *et al.*, 2005; Ramji *et al.*, 2002).

3.2.5. Effect on the cardiovascular system

Betel leaf is considered to provide strength to the heart and regulates irregular heart beat and blood pressure (<http://www.ejournalofdentistry.com/ebook/Is sue3/data/pages/8.swf>, 2012). By chewing betel leaves for few minutes (Chu, 2001), which includes cardio-acceleration, sweating and salivation. It induces catecholamine secretion from the adrenal cortex contributing to increase in stamina, heart rate, blood pressure, blood glucose levels and sympathetic neural activity.

3.2.6. Platelet Inhibition activity

The pathogenesis has platelet hyperactivity due to cardiovascular diseases (intravascular thrombosis). Piperbetol, ethylpiperbetol, piperol A and piperol B isolated from leaves, selectively inhibited platelet aggregation in a concentration dependent manner which induced by platelet activating factor (PAF) (Pisar *et al.*, 2007).

3.2.7. Immunomodulatory activity

The methanolic extract has lymphocyte proliferation, interferon-C receptors and the production of nitric oxide were measured in vitro. Further, the extract at different dose levels was studied in vivo for the humoral and cellular immune responses on mice immunized with sheep red blood cells. The result showed that it significantly suppressed haemagglutinin stimulated peripheral blood lymphocyte proliferation in a dose-dependent manner. The decrease in antibody titre and increased suppression of inflammation suggests possible immunosuppressive effect of extract on cellular and humoral response in mice (Sharma *et al.*, 2007). From past findings we can conclude that betel leaf a novel candidate for immunosuppressive activity. The same could be further evaluated for its anticancer activity or as a potential candidate in the treatment of autoimmune disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis, systemic lupus erythematous or emphysema (<http://www.ejournalofdentistry.com/ebook/Is sue3/data/pages/8.swf>, 2012).

3.3. Formulation of Food Products using Betel Leaves

Vernekar and Vijayalaxmi (2018) developed value added *papads* from the same in an order to increase the consumption of betel leaves to exploit their nutritional benefits. *Papads* were prepared by incorporating dehydrated betel leaves both *Kariyele* and *Ambadiyele* powder at 5, 7.5 and 10 per cent levels and evaluated organoleptically in comparison to control sample using 9- point hedonic scale. All the *papads* were found to be acceptable at 5 percent level of incorporation. *Kariyelepapad* found to have higher moisture 10.76 percent, fat 1.52 gm, vitamin-C 1.73 mg and iron 4.94 mg whereas *Ambadiyelepapad* had higher ash 3.75 gm, crude fiber 1.27 gm, β -carotene 413.41 μ g and calcium 252.15 mg.

Bhargava and Tyagi (2011) developed value added *Laddu*, *Namkeen* and cutlet by using betel leaves and mint leaves as control and then evaluated their acceptability among the population by sensory evaluation. Results revealed that cutlets were equally accepted while betel leaves *Laddu* and *Namkeen* were more accepted than mint leaves *Laddu* and *Namkeen* by the population. Moreover, none of the product was rated poor or very poor on a five point scale.

Roy and Guha (2015) developed a novel cupcake by incorporating essential oil of betel leaf. The textural properties of the cakes were measured by texture analyzer instrument; whereas the organoleptic properties were adjudged by human preferences using sensory tables containing 9-point hedonic scale. Price estimation was done considering all costs and charges. Finally, all parameters of the developed cake were compared with different cupcakes available in the market for ascertaining consumer acceptability of the newly developed product in terms of quality and market price. Results revealed that the Novel cupcake developed with 0.005 % (v/w) essential oil of betel leaf occupied the 1st place among the four developed novel cupcakes. However, it occupied 4th place among the nine cupcakes in the overall preference list prepared based on the textural and organoleptic qualities, though its market price was calculated to be comparable to all the leading cupcakes available in the market. This indicates that manufacturing of novel cupcake with essential oil of betel leaf would be a profitable and self-sustaining entrepreneurship.

The product *khakhra* prepared with the incorporation of betel leaves powder both *Kariyele* and *Ambadiyele* at 5, 7.5 and 10% level. *Khakhra* were prepared by using wheat flour as base ingredient along with betel leaves powder. The developed *khakhra* were evaluated organoleptically using nine point scale. *Khakhra* prepared with 5% of *Kariyele* and *Ambadiyele* powder was best acceptable and used for their nutrient computation. Results revealed that *khakhra* prepared with *Kariyele* powder was found to be high in moisture (12.76 %), protein (12.87 gm) and vitamin-C (2.79 mg) whereas *Ambadiyelekhakhra* was found to be high in ash (2.23 gm), crude fiber (2.97 gm), carbohydrate (69.66 gm), β - carotene (378.68 μ g), calcium (215.85 mg) and iron (7.30 mg) (Vernekar *et al.*, 2018).

4. Conclusion

From above literatures we can conclude that betel leaves possess therapeutic activities such as antioxidant activity, anti-microbial, anti-ulcerogenic, anti-haemolytic activity, anti-diabetic, immune-modulatory, anti-inflammatory, gastro protective etc. Betel leaves also contains numerous nutrients such as vitamins and minerals, especially calcium, iron, potassium and β -carotene. The plant leaves also used from ancient times in treatment of various diseases like bad breath, boils and abscesses, conjunctivitis, constipation, headache, itches, mastitis, leucorrhoea, cuts and injuries. As researches revealed that betel leaves are fit for treating various disease conditions further investigation on betel leaf may be execute to study the detailed mechanism of action for different diseases which will be beneficial for human begins.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

I would like to express my deep and sincere gratitude to my co-author, Ms. Lakhwinder Kaur (Head of Department of Home Science, KVA DAV College for Women, Karnal) for co-operating and believing in me. I would like to give special thanks to my family and friends for encouraging me for my research work and other projects.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict about the review paper and publication between both the authors.

References

- [1] Varier PS (1995) Indian Medicinal Plants a Compendium of 500 species. Orient Longman Publication, Chennai, India Vol 4: 279-280.
- [2] Guha (2006) P. Betel leaf: The neglected Green Gold of India. *J Hum Ecol.* 19(2): 87-93.
- [3] Walter TM, Sofia HN (2007) Effect of consumption of thamboolam (conventional betel chewing) in traditional siddha medicine. <http://openmed.nic.in/2223/01/Thamboolam.pdf>.
- [4] Jaganath IB, Ng teik L (2000) *Piper betle*. In Herbs-The Green Pharmacy of Malaysia; MARDI: Malaysia pp; 81 – 83.
- [5] Balasubrahmanyam V R, Rawat A K S (1990) Betel vine (*Piper betel*, Piperaceae) *Economic Botany* Vol.44: No 4: pp: 540-543.
- [6] Amonkar A J, Nagabhushan M, D'Souza A V, Bhide S V (1986) Hydroxychavicol: A new phenolic antimutagen from betel leaf. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 24 (12): 1321 – 1324.
- [7] Padma P R, Lalitha V S, Amonkar A J, Bhide S V (1989) Anticarcinogenic effect of betel leaf extract against tobacco carcinogens. *Cancer Letters* 45 pp: 195 – 202.
- [8] Mazura M P, Nuziah H, Rasadah M A, Ling S K (2007) Evaluation of *Piper betle* on platelet activating factor (PAF) receptor binding activities. *Malaysian Journal of Science* 26 (1) pp: 79 – 83.
- [9] Ramji N, Ranji N, Iyer R, Chandrasekaran S (2002) Phenolic antibacterials from *Piper betle* in the prevention of halitosis. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 83: 149 – 152.
- [10] Dasgupta N, De N (2004) Antioxidant activity of *Piper betle* L. Leaf extract in vitro. *Food Chemistry* 88: 219 – 224.
- [11] Arambewela L S R, Arawwawala L D A M, Ratnasooriya W D (2005) Antidiabetic activities of aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Piper betle* leaves in rats. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 102: 239 – 245.

- [12] Agarwal T, Singh R, Shukla AD, Waris I, Gujrati A (2012) Comparative analysis of antibacterial activity of four Piper betle varieties. *Advances in Applied Science Research* 3 (2): 698-705.
- [13] Longvah T, Ananthan R, Bhaskar K, Venkaiah K (2017) Indian Food Composition Table. National Institute of Nutrition (ICMR) Department of Health Research, Hyderabad, Telgana, India.
- [14] Ghosh R, Darin K, Nath P, Panchali (2014) An overview of various *piper* species for their biological activities. *International Journal of Pharma Research and Review*. 3(1): 6775.
- [15] Vernekar AA, Vijaylaxmi K G, Suvarna V C (2018) Development of value added product from dehydrated betel leaves powder. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 7(9): 615-624.
- [16] Sugumaran M, Poornima M, Venkatraman S, Lakshmi M, Srinivasansethuvani (2011) Chemical composition and antimicrobial activity of sirugamani variety of Piper betle Linn Leaf oil. *Journal of Pharmacy Research* 4 (10): 3424-3426.
- [17] Bajpai V, Sharma D, Kumar B, Madhusudanan KP (2010) Profiling of *Piper betle* Linn. Cultivars by direct analysis in real time mass spectrometric technique. *Biomedical Chromatography*. 24 (12): 1283-1286.
- [18] Kumar N, Misra P, Dube A (2010) *Piper betle* Linn. A maligned Pan-Asiatic plant with an array of pharmacological activities and prospects for drug discovery. *Curr Sci*. 99: 922-32.
- [19] The Wealth of India, The dictionary of Indian raw materials and industrial products (1992) Raw material, revised. New Delhi, (Publication and information directorate, (CSIR) pp: 5.
- [20] Sudrik S, Fegade S, Shinde M (2012) Anthelmintic Activity of *Piper Betle* Linn, (Paan/ Nagavalli) Aqueous Extract", *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences* 3(4) pp: 467-470.
- [21] Chu N S (2001) Effects of Betel Chewing on the Central and Autonomic Nervous Systems", *J Biomed Sci*. (8) pp: 229-236.
- [22] Mula S, Banerjee D, Patro B S, Barik A, Bandopadhyay S K, Chattopadhyay S (2008) Inhibitory property of the *Piper betle* phenolics against photosensitization induced biological damages", *Bioorganic and medicinal chemistry* (16) pp: 2932-2938.
- [23] Santhanam G, Nagarajan S (1990) Wound healing activity of *Curcuma aromatica* and *Piper betle* *Fitoterapia* (61) pp: 458-459.
- [24] Chatterjee A, Pakrashi S C (1995) *Treatise of Indian Medicinal Plants* (CSIR Publication New Delhi) pp: 26.
- [25] Deshpande S M, Upadhyay R R, Singh R P (1970) Chemical study of Piper betel leaves. *Current Sci*. (39) pp: 372.
- [26] Rawat A K S, Tripathi R D, Khan A J, Balasubrahmanyam V R (1989) Essential oil components as markers for identification of *Piper betle* L. Cultivars. *Biochem. Syst. Ecol.* (17) pp: 38-55.
- [27] Chandra T, Sadique J, Somasundaram S (1987) Effect of *Elipta alba* on inflammation and liver injury. *Fitoterapia* (58) pp: 23-31.
- [28] Vossen H A M V, Wessel M (2000) *Plant Resources of South-East Asia Stimulants*. Backhuys Publisher, Netherlands pp: 102-106.
- [29] Amalia H, Sitompul R, Hutauruk J, Andrianjah Mun'im A (2008) Effectiveness of *Piper betle* leaf infusion as a palpebral skin antiseptic. *Universa Medicina* 28(2) pp: 83-91.
- [30] Evans P H, Bowers W S, Funk E J (1984) Identification of Fungicidal and Nematocidal Components in the Leaves of Piper Betel (Piperaceae). *Journal of Food Agricultural and Chemistry* (32) pp: 1254-1256.
- [31] Bangar G P, Rao R E, Varma K C (1966) Antimicrobial activity of leaves and oil of *Piper betle*. *Ind. J. Pharm.* (28) pp: 327.
- [32] Ali S M, Mehta R K (1970) Preliminary pharmacological and anthelmintic studies of the essential oil of *Piper betle*. *Ind. J. Pharm.* (32) pp: 132.
- [33] Jesonbabu J, Spandana N, Lakshmi K A (2012) In vitro antimicrobial potentialities of chloroform extracts of Ethanomedicinal plant against clinically isolated human pathogens. *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, 4(3), pp: 624-626.
- [34] Agarwal T, Singh R (2012) Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity of Piper betel cultivars. *Novus International Journal of Pharmaceutical Technology* 1(1) pp: 50-58.

- [35] Chakraborty D, Shah B (2011) Antimicrobial, antioxidative and antihemolytic activity of Piper betel leaf extracts. *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.* 3(3), pp: 192-199.
- [36] Majumdar B, Ray C S G, Ray A, Bandyopadhyay SK (2003) Effect of ethanol extract of *Piper betle* Linn leaf on healing of NSAID induced experimental ulcer a novel role of free radical scavenging action. *Indian J Exp Biol.* 41(4) pp: 311-5.
- [37] Arambewela L S R, Arawwawala L D A M, Ratnasooriya W D (2004) Gastroprotective activities of Sri Lankan *Piper betle* leaf extracts in rats. *SLAAS 60th Annual Session* pp: 117.
- [38] Verma S, Gupta M L, Dutta A, Sankhwar S, Shukla S K, Flora S J (2010) Modulation of ionizing radiation induced oxidative imbalance by semi-fractionated extract of *Piper betle*: an in vitro and in vivo assessment. *Oxid. Med. Cell Longev.* 3(1) pp: 44-52.
- [39] Antimicrobial Activity of Psidium Guajava and *Piper Betle* Extracts on Selected Foodborne Bacteria (2006) <http://psasir.upm.edu.my/133/>.
- [40] Manigauha A, Ali H, Maheshwari M U (2009) Antioxidant activity of ethanolic extract of Piper betel leaves", *Journal of Pharmacy Research* 2(3) pp:194-95.
- [41] Rathee J S, Patro B S, Mula S, Gamre S, Chattopadhyay S (2006) Antioxidant Activity of Piper betel Leaf Extract and Its Constituents. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 54(24) pp: 9046–9054.
- [42] Pin K Y, Chuah A L, Rashih A A, Mazura M P, Fadzureena J, Vimala S, Rasadah M A (2010) Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of Extracts of betel leaves (*Piper betle*) from solvents with different polarities. *Journal of Tropical Forest Science* 22(4) pp: 448– 455.
- [43] Arambewela L, Arawwawala M, Rajapaksa D (2006) Piper betle: a potential natural antioxidant. *International Journal of Food Science and Technology* 41 (1) pp: 10–14.
- [44] Chandra V, Tripathi S, Verma N K, Singh DP, Chaudhary S K, Roshan A (2011) Piper betel: phytochemistry, traditional use & pharmacological activity-a review. *IJPRD* 4(4), pp. 216 -223.
- [45] Ramji N, Ramji N, Iyer R, Chandrasekaran S (2002) Phenolic antibacterial from *Piper betle* in the prevention of halitosis. *J. Ethnopharmacology* 83 pp:149-152.
- [46] Areca nut: To chew or not to chew? (2012) <http://www.ejournalofdentistry.com/ebook/Issue3/data/pages/8.swf>.
- [47] Pissar MMd, Hashim N, Ali R M, Sui K L (2007) Evaluation of *Piper betle* on Platelet Activating Factor (PAF) Receptor Binding Activities. *Malaysian Journal of Science* 26 (1) pp: 79-83.
- [48] Sharma J D, Sharma L, Yadav P (2007) Antifertility Efficacy of *Piper betle* Linn. (Petiole) on Female Albino Rats. *Asian J. Exp. Sci.* 21(1), pp. 145-150.
- [49] Vernekar A A, Vijaylaxmi K G (2018) Development of *Papad* from dehydrated betel leaves (*Piper betel L.*) Powder. *International Journal of Food Science and Nutrition* 3(5): 33-38.
- [50] Bhargava A, Tyagi G (2011) Acceptability of betel and mint leaves recipes among the population by sensory evaluation. *Asian Journal of home science.* 2:137-139.
- [51] Roy A, Guha P (2015) Development of a novel cupcake with unique properties of essential oil of betel leaf (*Piper betle L.*) for sustainable entrepreneurship. *J Food Sci Technol* 52(8):4885–4894